

Lost & Found

Developed by: Owen Gottlieb, Ian Schreiber, RIT – MAGIC Spell Studios, Convergent

Article contributed by: Matthes Groetzner

Keywords

Community Building, Competition, Cooperation, Economics, Empathy, History, Law, Medieval History, Religious Law, Religion, Resource Management, Strategic Decision-making, Tragedy of the Commons

Figure 1. Key visual from *Lost & Found* (Owen Gottlieb, Ian Schreiber, RIT – MAGIC Spell Studios, Convergent). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Lost & Found is a historically analog strategy game series, later adapted into digital formats, developed by its two lead designers, Owen Gottlieb and Ian Schreiber, from the Rochester Institute of Technology (RIT). The first game in the series was published in 2017 by the MAGIC Center Initiative in Religion, Culture & Policy, and is the main focus of this article. During this game, players aged 14 and above slip into up to five roles of medieval citizens of a 12th-

century North African town, where each of them will struggle to find balance between the needs of their family and those of their entire community in order for all to thrive. In collaboration as well as in competition with their fellow citizens, the players have to utilize their limited resources in a struggle to address dilemmas, overcome crises, and avert disasters that threaten to destroy the community (Lost & Found, 2018; Gottlieb, 2021; Gottlieb et al., 2017). The room for the individual and communal trade-off decisions is defined and limited by the historically accurate, religious-based laws and legal systems of the time, which serve as a guidepost for behavior. By highlighting the pro-social aspects of religious legal systems, the game fosters greater discourse and understanding of how these systems have shaped the foundations of modern law. Developing religious literacy in this way can enrich our understanding of community-building today (Gottlieb, 2017; Gottlieb, 2021; Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020a; Lost & Found, 2018).

Facts

Release date:	2017 (Lost & Found – first game), 2017 (Lost & Found: Order in the Court – second game), 2020 (Lost & Found: New Harvest – third game)
Developer:	Owen Gottlieb, Ian Schreiber, RIT – MAGIC Spell Studios, Convergent
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–5 players (Second game: 3–5 players)
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	Approximately 60–90 minutes (Second game: 30-60 minutes)
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Space for group activity, room, table, or floor (optional)
Material:	Game box contains all required materials.
Price:	61.99\$ (First Game), 55.99\$ (Second Game), 66.99\$ (Third Game)

Resonance & Criticism

Since its initial release in 2017, the Lost & Found series has won several awards and recognitions, which are displayed on its homepage. It was an Indiecade Nominee (Indiecade, 2019), part of the SAAM Arcade Official Selection (Smithsonian American Art Museum, 2018), won the Bronze Medal at the International Serious Play Awards 2018, was nominated for Best Non-Digital Game at the International Academic Conference on Meaningful Play in 2018 and again in 2022, and was a Finalist at the James Paul Gee Learning Games Awards 2021 in the Middle School and Up category. It was also included in three additional Official Selections at Open World Arcade and Now Play This London in 2019, as well as at the Boston Festival of Independent Games (FIG) in both 2018 and 2022 (Homepage – Lost & Found, 2018). The game is considered to have strong potential as a teaching tool for history. In an experiment, some history students reported that after playing the game they would begin learning from ‘experience’ rather than memorizing. Experiencing historically accurate legal systems and

applying them to simulated real situations may help solidify understanding of the past (Gottlieb, 2021; Houghton, 2022).

Game Principle & Process

Within the first game of the series, each player represents a family and a job-related role in a small community, such as a cowherd or a potter. The goal is to complete at least three of five family responsibility cards, which require significant sums of dinarim (the game's main resource). Players must also collectively complete at least six of ten communal responsibility cards, which allow for pooled contributions. The game ends after a set number of turns. Failure to complete enough communal responsibilities results in a collective loss. Players who meet family goals win if the community survives, so just some, all, or no players can win.

On a turn, a player first draws resource cards, which include personal resources and items that belong to themselves, other players, or strangers. Using others' resources is treated as theft and has potential endgame consequences. Next, the player draws an event card inspired by historically accurate situations. Events may present rewards, moral dilemmas, or crises that require cooperation. Players must weigh following the law, breaking it for short-term gain, or exceeding requirements for long-term benefits. If a player cannot pay for the required resources, they go destitute, causing all players to lose. After resolving events, a player may return a lost item to clear space in their hand. They can then contribute resources to a family responsibility (requiring full payment) or a communal responsibility (allowing partial contributions). The turn ends with discarding resources until the hand limit is reached, and the game continues. Players must balance personal goals with communal needs, facing constant tension between individual success and community survival (Gottlieb et al., 2017).

The game's rules are tied to and based on Moses Maimonides Mishneh Torah, a religious law code. The legal scholar, physician, philosopher, and rabbi distilled hundreds of years of Jewish law within his work (Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020a; Gottlieb, 2021). As a tool for teaching historic systems and societies, the game connects to emphasize the power of “experiential learning”. It is able to simulate experience for its players, who can then reflect, think, and act according to it (Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020b; Houghton, 2022; Institute for Experiential Learning, n.d). With the game's general structure of balancing family and communal needs, it also addresses issues such as the “tragedy of the commons”, although it is not specifically designed to do so. Players get rewarded based on both their resource management and their reputation within the community (Gottlieb, 2017).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The initial aim of the game is to expand the discourse surrounding religious legal systems, broaden the understanding of societal development, and bring religious literacy to more people. It teaches the pro-social aspects of religious-based law systems, such as collaboration, cooperation, and sustainability of governance and community. This makes the central purpose

of the game to serve as a learning artifact for both formal and informal environments (Gottlieb, 2021; Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020a).

It reaches its initial goal through experiential learning. Playing the game under its historical, religious, and law-based rules simulates experience. Reflecting on this experience helps players weave these teachings into their way of thinking and potentially act on them. The emphasis on player interaction within a community also highlights a secondary learning objective. Players can learn historical thinking and historical empathy, which could be key factors in truly understanding history. Especially when viewed from modern standpoints. This makes the learning process not only about knowledge but also about skill (Houghton, 2022). The resulting experiential learning cycle can positively affect players' future behavior (Institute for Experiential Learning, n.d). Through historical experience, players could thus learn to be more responsible citizens of our modern, pluralistic democracy (Lost & Found, 2018).

The game's creators and collaborators have suggested that this game (and games like it) could be included in learning environments as history-teaching tools. It therefore holds the potential to play its part in maximizing the diversity of teaching opportunities and learning experiences (for a certain range of disciplines). These are historical, legal, ethical, art, history, and religious studies, given their historic accuracy (Houghton, 2022).

Effectiveness

There is little evidence or data on the game “Lost & Found” 's actual effectiveness. No real numbers are given. However, in reflective observations during the game's creative process, the developers found that it initially did not spark discussion about the game's context and meaning. Role-play-oriented play and design were implemented to increase the players interest and engagement, as a more “humorous” way to play and learn. This aspiration has led to the development of the second game in the series, which further sought to incorporate players' own thoughts and ideas into the gameplay (Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020a; Gottlieb & Schreiber, 2020b). Simultaneously, there has been some feedback from history students while reflecting on how the game affected their learning progress. Some stated that there was no personal difference in learning the conventional way. Others recalled the ability to truly understand the essence of the historic material in question whilst playing the game (Houghton, 2022).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Given that the Lost & Found series explores past times and cultural contexts, some of its historically accurate depictions might clash with modern views (Houghton, 2022).

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Katsarov

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